

Abstract of Contribution 261

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A web-based map viewer collating surface and subsurface geodata in the context of deep geothermal activities all over Europe

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A web-based map viewer is developed within the European Horizon 2020 project MEET and intended as a one-stop solution to cater to the wide spectrum of stakeholders that are interested in deep geothermal exploration and project development. The webtool will support future users in the geothermal community to access geospatial data at European scale and to be able to identify and find existing geodata at national or smaller scales. At the culmination of the MEET project, the outcome of investigations at local scale (demo sites and analogue sites) will be transferred and upscaled to other potential regions all over Europe.

The incorporated information ranges widely from traditional geological data to the information on the key players in geothermal sector. This webtool utilizes Opensource software like OpenLayers, PostGIS and GeoServer to produce the interactive data visualization. The data is grouped into different categories like geology, land and soil, environment, general information, powerplants etc. but can be effectively brought together by switching on multiple map layers and adjusting their transparency. We have aimed to fruitfully utilize the capabilities of Open Data while ensuring the trustworthiness by properly attributing the data sources.

We aim to combine this webtool with a decision-making tool which is another outcome of the MEET project. These, together with a parameter catalogue designed to offer more details about the various geothermal parameters would serve as a guiding trio for anyone who plans to deeply understand the landscape of geothermal energy sector in Europe.